

Thematic DCC

Bottleneck project

Project description form

1. General information

Project title

Untangling FAIR implementation in the Dutch SSH

Relevant Thematic DCC Domain(s)

Life Sciences and Health Natural and Engineering Sciences Social Sciences and Humanities

Responsible institution

Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam - Erasmus School of Social and Behavioural Sciences (ESSB)

Burgemeester Oudlaan 50

3062 PA Rotterdam

Other applying institution(s)

Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam - Erasmus Research Services (ERS)

Burgemeester Oudlaan 50

3062 PA Rotterdam

DANS-KNAW

Anna van Saksenlaan 51

2593 HW Den Haag

Project leader(s)

Title, first name, initials, surname	Affil.	Dept.	Expertise	Role(s)
Dr. T.E. (Tom) Emery	EUR	ESSB	Research infrastructure, demography	Project leader
Dr. A.M. (Angelica Maria) Maineri	EUR	ESSB	FAIR Implementation	Work package 3 and 4 leader
B. (Borana) Lushaj, M.A.	EUR	ERS	Data management	Work package 2 leader
Dr. J. (Jetze) Toubert	DANS-KNAW		Data management	Work package 1 leader

Main field of research

	Code/Field of research:
Main field of research:	37.40.00 Databases for humanities

Other field(s) of research (if applicable):	27.50.00	Social and economic history
	27.60.00	Cultural history
	37.10.00	Software for humanities
	38.10.00	Microeconomics
	38.30.00	Econometrics
	40.50.00	Social and Organizational Psychology
	41.90.00	Educational Sciences
	44.20.00	Political science.
	45.90.00	Sociology
	47.90.00	Communication science
	48.90.00	Demography
	51.90.00	Development studies

Abstract (max 500 words)

FAIR implementation in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH)-domain appears as a tangled bundle of yarn. Misalignments along several dimensions between different stakeholders (Research, Infrastructure, Policy and Heritage) make for a convoluted knot of technical choices and decisional processes. Despite ongoing attempts to remedy this, for instance through national research infrastructures such as ODISSEI and CLARIAH, technical and organisational complexities still characterise Research Data Management (RDM) in the domain¹. In this project, we aim to untangle these complexities, gaining understanding of the dynamics at play in the process. . The goal is to facilitate a coordinated approach to managing research data in a Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) way.

RDM experts in the Dutch SSH domain face a combination of challenges. On the one hand, they are responsible for the technical implementation of a diversity of community-specific FAIR-enabling choices, arising from heterogeneous types of data and disciplinary methodologies. On the other hand, they need to foster interoperability at the level of the SSH domain, to facilitate ground-breaking interdisciplinary research. The research institutions where they work have developed high-level policies that mandate the generation of FAIR research output. But this has often yet to translate into consequential FAIR implementation strategies, which navigate the complex interplay of institutional structures, technological affordances, educational levels and expertise available. The current project aims to foster a more coordinated approach to FAIR implementation within the SSH-domain, manoeuvring between high level generic recommendations and specific practices on the work floor. It will result in an Action plan to address the technical and socio-organisational bottlenecks the SSH is facing regarding FAIR implementation at the national level.

¹ <https://odissei-data.nl>; <https://www.clariah.nl>

We have identified two primary stakeholder groups that would benefit from this project. The first group includes research infrastructure, governmental organisations and heritage institutions (INFRA) (e.g., CLARIAH, ODISSEI, DANS, UKB, Statistics Netherlands, NDE), mainly responsible for developing and maintaining FAIR technical, curatorial, and archival standards across the SSH-domain. The second group includes Research Performing Organizations (RPOs) (e.g., universities, research institutes), which pursue the implementation of community-specific FAIR standards, both in their policies and services, and through initiatives led by the research groups they host.

As alluded to above, alignment between and within these stakeholder groups is hindered by structural divergence along two dimensions. First, the heterogeneous and often implicit technical standards for FAIR data management adopted by different entities - within both the INFRA and RPO stakeholder groups - make it difficult to create a truly interoperable SSH infrastructure. Second, the organisational structures that are charged with developing FAIR-enabling policies have yet to operationalize FAIR data management within their strategies and service portfolios. With decision-making bodies being placed at different levels in each organisation, dialogue about harmonisation of SSH FAIR technical standards and related services is hindered.

The project is divided into two main components. First, we will conduct a preliminary reconnaissance of organisation-specific FAIR technical practices and decisional structures (see WP1 & WP2). Second, we will organise a 2-day “unconference”-event to discuss the results of the technical and organisational mapping exercises and facilitate decision-making on how to move forward. The event will inform the creation of an Action plan towards FAIR implementation in the SSH (see WP3), which will in turn be a complement to more general documents such as the TDCC-SSH Roadmap and the SSH Sector Plan.

Popular project title and public summary

NL

Ontwarren van FAIR implementatie in de Nederlandse Sociale en Geesteswetenschappen

Dit project brengt verschillende belanghebbenden samen, om de technische en organisatorische barrières te slechten die op dit moment de Nederlandse Sociale en Geesteswetenschappen (SSH) ervan weerhouden te profiteren van Research Data Management volgens de hoogste standaarden. Het project onderzoekt de technologische en organisatorische praktijken bij verschillende instituten en biedt een platform om de dialoog hierover aan te gaan. Dit resulteert in een actieplan met daarin zowel een weergave van de huidige situatie als haalbare stappen om de implementatie van de FAIR-principes in het Nederlandse SSH-datalandschap gecoördineerd aan te pakken.

ENG

Untangling FAIR implementation in the Dutch Social Sciences and Humanities

The project brings together different stakeholders to solve the technical and organisational complexities that prevent the Dutch Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) to fully leverage the opportunities offered by the highest research data management standards. The project investigates the technological and organisational practices at different institutes and provides a forum to engage in conversations about them. The resulting Action Plan document provides a snapshot of the current situation and its problems, together with actionable steps to ensure a more coordinated approach towards the implementation of the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability (FAIR) principles in the Dutch SSH data landscape.

2. Project information

Describe the requested project.

2.1. Description of the project

Please describe the proposed project.

FAIR² implementation in the SSH-domain appears as a tangled bundle of yarn. Misalignments along several dimensions between different stakeholders (Research, Infrastructure, Policy and Heritage) make for a convoluted knot of technical choices and decisional processes. In this project, we aim to untangle the technical and organisational complexities which currently characterise Research Data Management (RDM) in the SSH-domain. The goal is to facilitate a coordinated approach to managing research data in a FAIR way (see Figure 1 below).

Statement of the problem

Research Data Management (RDM) experts in the Dutch SSH Research, Infrastructure, Policy and Heritage milieu work to ensure that data are published in a Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) way. Within a rapidly-evolving ecosystem, they need to balance between diverging interests. On the one hand, they must facilitate the technical implementation of a diversity of community-specific FAIR-enabling choices, arising from a variety of data types and disciplinary methodologies. On the other hand, they should promote interoperability at the level of the SSH domain – an essential step to facilitate ground-breaking interdisciplinary research. Meanwhile, there is a discrepancy between institutional aspirations and the provisions in place on the workflow to realise those aims. Many research institutions have developed high-level policies that mandate the generation of FAIR research output. However, they still need to develop effective FAIR implementation strategies which navigate the complex interplay of institutional structures, technological affordances, educational levels and expertise available.

The interweaving of technical and organisational complexities manifests itself in myriad ways. One example may suffice to illustrate how this situation holds SSH communities back from fully leveraging FAIR implementation to ensure long-term sustainability for the research data they produce. FAIR policies and guidelines often state the requirement of describing (meta)data using FAIR vocabularies, in line with FAIR principle I2³. At the implementation stage, however, many problems arise: SSH disciplinary communities often work with granular and fuzzy concepts which require additional time and expertise investment to be turned into ontologies or structured vocabularies.; when vocabularies or ontologies exist, these are not applied broadly because researchers within the discipline are not aware of them, or because the technical skills necessary are not part of the traditional training of a SSH practitioner. On the other hand, data curators are prohibitively costly to budget in⁴. In addition, from a governance perspective, there is no single centrally maintained repository for semantic artefacts of SSH (sub)disciplines and research communities. At the same time, institutional repositories tasked with curating the data generated by their researchers and research communities are still in the process of developing their FAIR-enabling services and strategies. It is unclear when or whether institutional repositories can or should take up the task of providing interoperability services for their own research output and, if so, how they can engage with discipline-specific communities.

The solution to this problem is manifold, and requires the involvement of different stakeholders, including:

- researchers and data experts who work together to transform specialised knowledge into semantic artefacts that can be reused;
- technology providers for building a repository for vocabularies;
- experts of linked data/semantic web who can support the integration of semantic artefacts into the SSH data lifecycle;
- RPO management who recognizes that work of this kind goes well beyond what the traditional publication cycle entails.

² Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. Wilkinson, Mark D., Michel Dumontier, IJsbrand Jan Aalbersberg, Gabrielle Appleton, Myles Axton, Arie Baak, Niklas Blomberg, et al. 'The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship'. *Scientific Data* 3, no. 1 (December 2016): 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

³ I2: "(Meta)data use vocabularies that follow the FAIR principles". See <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/i2-metadata-use-vocabularies-follow-fair-principles/>

⁴ See the work on semantic artefacts done in the FAIRsFAIR-project: Gerard Coen, 'Introduction to Semantic Artefacts', <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3549375>.

This project aims at fostering a more coordinated approach to FAIR implementation involving diverse stakeholders to help solve the technical and organisational bottlenecks specific to the SSH domain, which can then be translated into an Action plan that will be proposed at the national level.

Stakeholders

We will involve two primary stakeholder groups:

- Infrastructure, governmental organisations, archival entities and heritage institutions (**INFRA**s) (e.g., CLARIAH, ODISSEI, SSHOC-NL, DANS, UKB, Statistics Netherlands, NDE). These are mainly responsible for developing and maintaining SSH domain-wide FAIR technical, curatorial, and archival standards. They often aggregate data from diverse sub-communities, and while fostering interoperability across them, they often have to give up some community-specific granularity.
- Research Performing Organizations (**RPO**s) (universities, research institutes). They pursue the implementation of FAIR community-/discipline-specific standards in their policies and services, and through initiatives led by the research groups they host. This group is highly heterogeneous, and involves people at different levels (e.g. management, research support, academic staff).

Currently, alignment between these stakeholder groups is hindered by structural divergence along two dimensions.

First, the heterogeneous and often implicit technical standards for FAIR data management adopted by different entities make it difficult to create a truly interoperable SSH infrastructure. Choices made over the years concerning the technological systems, e.g. data repositories, together with often poorly documented metadata practices, limit the opportunities for domain-wide collaboration and federation.

Second, the organisational structures place the responsibility of FAIR policies at different levels in each organisation, making it harder to arrange fruitful dialogue. For instance, RDM and FAIR experts who work closely with researchers at universities are normally based at the Local Digital Competence Centers (L-DCCs), whereas FAIR implementation policies at universities are often developed by management bodies. As suggested in an upcoming report by Kees den Heijer, DCC liaison at SURF, the L-DCCs' position within the university structure as well as the methods they adopt to oversee FAIR implementation varies by institution. As a result, those in charge of developing and signing off on FAIR implementation policies across institutions may not even meet with representatives from L-DCCs, due to differences in the "circles" they engage with.

In preparing this project proposal, we have secured the interest of a variety of representatives of these two groups of stakeholders. We point to these efforts under the heading ***Fit within landscape and added value w.r.t. ongoing projects***, below. We will continue to follow up with dedicated steps to secure further buy-in, as outlined under the heading ***2.3 Communication strategy and dissemination***, below.

In sum, this project aims to untie the knots resulting from the interweaving of technical and organisational complexities in research data management across the SSH-domain, conditioned by the specific interests of disciplinary communities and the generic demands of domain-wide interoperability. The project is divided into two main components. First, we will conduct a preliminary reconnaissance of the organisation-specific FAIR technical practices and decisional structures (see WP1 & WP2). Second, we will organise a 2-day *unconference* event to discuss the results of the technological inventory and the organisational mapping and facilitate decision-making on how to move forward. The event will inform the creation of an Action plan towards FAIR implementation in the SSH (see WP3), which will in turn be a complement to more general documents such as the TDCC-SSH Roadmap⁵ and the SSH Sector Plan⁶.

⁵ See <https://www.nwo.nl/sites/nwo/files/media-files/Roadmap%20TDCC%20SSH.pdf/>

⁶ See <https://www.sectorplan-ssh.nl/>

Figure 1: Outline of the project.
(Photo credits: MissVicki and Van3ssa_, Pixabay)

Project Timeline

Project Timeline 2024-2025

Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug
WP1: Technical mapping											
WP2: Organisational mapping											
				WP3: Unconference and Action plan							
WP4: Coordination											

Roadmap ambition/activity cluster/challenge

NES	SSH	LSH
<input type="checkbox"/> Digital competencies and training	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> FAIRification of data and software	<input type="checkbox"/> Strengthen good data stewardship and harmonise data access practises
<input type="checkbox"/> Fragmented landscape	<input type="checkbox"/> Raising awareness	<input type="checkbox"/> Enhance the interoperability of digital solutions and resources
<input type="checkbox"/> Interoperability of data and of workflows	<input type="checkbox"/> Knowledge enhancement	<input type="checkbox"/> Strengthen the capacity and expertise base in digital research
<input type="checkbox"/> Long-term preservation and maintenance of research software	<input type="checkbox"/> Addressing pressing issues	
<input type="checkbox"/> Guidance about dealing with IP and legal issues	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Building a network	
<input type="checkbox"/> Collaboration between disciplines across the domain for adoption of FAIR practices		

Project duration

12 months (1 September 2024 - 31 August 2025)

Main goal(s) of the project

The project aims at gathering better understanding of how the FAIR principles are implemented at different organisations in the SSH, both at a technical and organisational level, discuss these during a community event and use the insights to co-create an Action plan document for guiding future developments, and investments.

Work packages

Work package	Leader
WP1: Technical mapping	Dr. J. Toubert (DANS)
WP2: Organisational mapping	B. Lushaj (EUR-ERS)
WP3: Unconference and Action plan	Dr. A.M. Maineri (EUR-ESSB)
WP4: Coordination	Dr. A.M. Maineri (EUR-ESSB)

WP1: Technical mapping

WP1 inquires into the **technical arrangements** in place for FAIR data management within the SSH domain. This will necessitate first of all an overview of established requirements for machine actionable findability, access, interoperability and reuse, emanating from the two prominent national-level disciplinary infrastructures (i.e. ODISSEI for the Social Sciences and CLARIAH for the Humanities). Simultaneously a reconstruction of the life cycle of research data generated by several representative research performing organisations will clarify at which moment in the research process these FAIR requirements are actually met, if at all. For instance: in the CLARIAH community it is required that, in compliance with FAIR principle R1.1 (licence for (meta)data records), a Creative Commons licence is attached to a dataset, whereas the ODISSEI User Policy requires a CC0 licence but only for metadata and does not require specific licences for datasets.⁷ Licences can be chosen in the repository in which a dataset is deposited, pointing to the archiving process as the stage in which this particular FAIR principle is being implemented, and to the repository as the system which makes it possible to observe this principle. In a similar way for the other FAIR principles, the specific guidelines as laid out by CLARIAH and ODISSEI will be mapped onto stages of the research process habitual in **RPOs**, with references to the **INFRA**s invoked as the process unfolds.

The work package includes the following tasks:

- 1) Set up FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs)⁸ to obtain a structured overview of the **technical requirements** for FAIR data management as stipulated by **disciplinary (sub)communities**. This will be done in collaboration with the PDI-SSH funded project FAIR Expertise Hub, which hosts FIP-workshops facilitators certified by the GO FAIR Foundation⁹.
Sep. 2024-Dec. 2024
- 2) Take a selection of datasets (or collections of datasets) falling within these disciplinary (sub)communities and model the **research data life cycle** contained in these datasets (e.g. data collection by individual researcher, data management at RPOs, data publication and archiving in INFRAs). Currently, datasets generated by the following organisational units are considered for inclusion in the selection:
 - a) Erasmus University, Faculty of Social Sciences
 - b) Leiden University, Faculty of Humanities
 - c) Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision
 - d) International Institute for Social History

The list may be further refined and expanded in light of the first outcomes as WP 1 and 2 are proceeding, though, including institutes dedicated to economic, psychological and/or linguistic research. We have already reached out to the Faculty of Social and Behavioral Sciences at Utrecht University, as well as the Max Planck Institute for Psycholinguistics, Nijmegen.

Sep. 2024-Dec. 2024

⁷ See Braukmann, R., Emery, T., & van der Meer, L. (2021). ODISSEI User Policy (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6597751>

⁸ Schultes, Erik, Barbara Magagna, Kristina Maria Hettne, Robert Pergl, Marek Suchánek, and Tobias Kuhn. 'Reusable FAIR Implementation Profiles as Accelerators of FAIR Convergence'. In *Advances in Conceptual Modeling*, edited by Georg Grossmann and Sudha Ram, 138–47. Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2020. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-65847-2_13.

⁹ <https://www.gofairfoundation.org>

- 3) Experiment with FAIR Assessment Tools¹⁰ and choose a suitable one to **test the FAIRness** of the datasets selected in (2.) against the FIPs set up in (1.).
Nov. 2024-Feb. 2025
- 4) For each of the datasets (or collections of datasets), retrace the stages within the research process at which **FAIR implementation choices** were made (drawing on the research data life cycle as individuated in 2.).
Dec. 2024-Mar. 2025

The results will be a map of FAIR implementation choices, the stages at which they are made, and the INFRA they make use of, for a sample of SSH-datasets originating with a representative selection of RPOs. This will be published in a FAIR way online and serve as input for the unconference, to be held in May 2025, which will, in turn, feed into the Action plan (see WP3).

WP1 Timeline 2024-2025

Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug
1) FIPs											
2) Model research data lifecycle											
	3) FAIR assessment										
	4) FIPs to Research data lifecycle										
								Uncon- ference			

For a successful implementation of WP1, the requested resources include an RDM expert working at DANS-KNAW (0.2 FTEs for 12 months) who will conduct the technical mapping. The creation of the FIPs will also see the collaboration of the Data Manager and the PDI-SSH Expertise Hub. To ensure collaboration of the institutes involved in the mapping of FIPs to the research life cycle (tasks 2-4) but without knowing beforehand who will be involved and for how much exactly, consultancy hours are budgeted among the material costs (see Section 3).

WP2: Organisational mapping

WP2 will identify concrete **organisational challenges** and **opportunities** in Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) for harmonising their RDM services and technologies with domain-wide FAIR standards in SSH. We will screen the current technologies, practices, and decisional structures of RPOs through the lens of established frameworks (e.g., FAIRsFAIR's [ACME-FAIR](#) framework) to establish which of these are relevant for FAIR-enablement in SSH.

We will also engage with representatives from L-DCCs and other stakeholders, including management representatives within RPOs, to record their views and experiences in setting or responding to technological, organisational, and policy priorities, specifically related to advancing FAIR implementation in SSH.

The above will be captured via:

- 1) Survey to L-DCC/RPO representatives to screen technology, organisational structures, and curation practices based on established FAIR-enablement frameworks to identify:
 - a) RDM policy and business priorities at RPOs and implementation efforts related to these
 - b) RPO's understanding of their "designated communities" and the degree and quality of engagement with specific faculties, departments or other discipline-specific communities
 - c) Technology choices and curation practices implemented at RPOs and relevant future plans
 - d) Their awareness of the methods, technology, and infrastructure landscape to facilitate interoperability and reusability for SSH data*Sep. 2024-Nov. 2024*
- 2) Interviews, informed by the survey results, with L-DCC coordinators, OSC members, policy and management decision makers to acquire a more nuanced picture of bottlenecks in:
 - a) Communication, stakeholder management and institutional buy-in
 - b) Development of FAIR-enabling policies and guidelines
 - c) Building expertise and awareness to enable FAIR-aware and FAIR-contributing SSH disciplinary communities within RPOs*Nov. 2024-Feb. 2025*

¹⁰ Examples include the [F-UJI Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool](#), the [FAIR-Checker](#), and the [FAIR Evaluation Services](#).

- 3) The findings from the investigations above will be shared with the RDM community at large prior to the Unconference, and will include:
- Visualisation of existing variation in RPOs in their RDM policy and business priorities, technologies, and workflows
 - Visualisation of stakeholder communication and decision bottlenecks for allocation of resources towards FAIR implementation in SSH
 - Visualisation of communication flows and needs between professional and data support in RPOs and disciplinary communities that would contribute to FAIR enablement

Feb. 2025-Mar. 2025

Our goal is to map the findings above to the research cycle model adopted in WP1 so as to establish a feedback loop with WP1's output of FAIR implementation choices and also inform the Unconference conversations and Action plan (see WP3) on how current technological and organisational affordances **facilitate** or **hinder** the generation of FAIR data following SSH domain-wide standards.

During the unconference L-DCC coordinators, policy makers and other key stakeholders (possibly including research deans or senior research representatives) are invited to develop internal or coordinated technological, organisational and methodological priorities towards FAIR-enabling services, to be adopted in the research data cycle.

Findings will be published in a FAIR way and distributed among participants and feedback will be sought from the community and advisory board for each of the WP tasks and milestones.

WP2 Timeline 2024-2025

Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug
1) Survey											
	2) Interviews										
			3) Analysis and outputs								
								Uncon- ference			

For a successful completion of WP2, the requested resources include a Research Data Steward (0.15 FTEs for 12 months) and an intern/student assistant (0.5FTEs for 12 months, see Material costs) based at EUR-ERS. Material costs also include vouchers to compensate participants in the survey and interviews (see Section 3).

WP3: Unconference and Action plan

The insights generated by the mappings carried out in WP1 and WP2 and openly shared will converge towards a 2-days *Unconference* (i.e. unconventional conference) event to be held in **May 2025** and the co-creation of an *Action plan* towards FAIR Implementation in the SSH, which are the main goals of WP3.

Unconference. By Unconference we mean “a participant-oriented meeting where the attendees decide on the agenda, discussion topics, workshops, and, often, even the time and venues”¹¹. Compared to a regular conference, an unconference is an appropriate setting to address the pressing issues surrounding FAIR Implementation in a way that lets different needs and perspectives emerge, and facilitates bottom-up solutions from the FAIR practitioners. The mission statement of the unconference is to set the agenda for a more coordinated approach to FAIR implementation in the SSH, flowing into an outline for an Action plan document. The program of the unconference will be co-created with its participants via a call for sessions, and will prioritise interactive sessions. Part of the event may take place in a hybrid format to maximise accessibility (the logistics will be taken care of by WP4). A professional consultant will be hired from the start of the project to help prepare and lead the event. The identification of the target audience will be informed by the organisational mapping (see WP2) to make sure that the key individuals from the different stakeholders are included.

Jan. 2025-May 2025

Action plan. The outcome of the unconference will be a document outlining an Action plan towards FAIR Implementation in the SSH. The document is intended as a thorough specification of FAIR Implementation challenges and solutions in the SSH, written by stakeholders active in the field, and to be used as complement to existing

¹¹ See page 1, Budd, Aidan, Holger Dinkel, Manuel Corpas, Jonathan C. Fuller, Laura Rubinat, Damien P. Devos, Pierre H. Khoueiry, et al. ‘Ten Simple Rules for Organizing an Unconference’. PLOS Computational Biology 11, no. 1 (29 January 2015): e1003905. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1003905>.

documents such as the TDCC-SSH Roadmap document and the SSH Sector Plan. Substantial parts of the Action plan will consist of the outcomes of WP1 and WP2. At the same time, interwoven with the technical and the organisational mappings, the Action plan will contain analysis of the dynamics at play within the research and infrastructural landscape on a more conceptual level.

After the unconference, participants will be able to indicate their availability to join the Action plan core writing team. Moreover, an open consultation will be held after the unconference and before the publication of the Action plan document, to ensure a wide representation of the SSH field in the document. The Action plan document will consist of four main components:

1. A description of the context. Informed by the mappings of WP1 and WP2, the document will include an overview of FAIR Implementation solutions and challenges in the Dutch SSH landscape.
2. A list of milestones and outcomes to be achieved to fill the identified gaps, including the stakeholders that should be involved for each of them. This will be the main outcome of the unconference event.
3. A documentation of the risks and mitigation strategies to be taken into account in the implementation of the Action plan. Input for this section will also arise from the unconference event.
4. A description of KPIs and progress monitoring, which will be written by the core writing team.

Once published, the Action plan document will be publicly shared and sent to relevant stakeholders, including funders and RPOs' and INFRAs' management.

May 2025-Aug. 2025

WP3 Timeline 2025

Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug
				Unconference: preparations							
						Unconference: call for sessions					
								Unconference			
								Action plan: writing			
									Action plan consultation		
											Action plan publication

For a successful completion of WP3, the whole project team will provide input, under the coordination of the Data manager (0.15FTEs or 12 months, based at EUR-ESSB). Material costs are budgeted to cover the expenses of the Unconference and accommodation expenses of organisers and speakers. Given the crucial role of the Unconference and its unconventional format, an external consultant will be hired at the start of the project to ensure a smooth organisation and execution of the event. Production costs are budgeted to make the Action plan effective also from a visual perspective, and residual consultancy hours will be used to compensate time for the core writing team (besides the time invested by the Project team) (see Section 3).

WP4: Coordination

For a successful outcome, the project requires coordination not only across the project partners but also across the stakeholders that will be involved in the mapping phases (see WP1 and WP2) and in the final event for the co-creation of the Action plan (see WP3). To this end, WP4 takes care of the coordination of the project and community/network engagement.

Tasks within WP4 include:

- Project administration, monitoring and reporting;
- Coordination of communications across project partners (e.g. press releases, event announcements, dissemination of outputs);
- Coordination of logistics for digital and physical events and workshops.

These tasks will be mostly carried out by a Project manager (0.15 FTEs for 12 months) based in the ODISSEI Coordination Team (CT) at EUR-ESSB. Material costs related to organising in-person meetings throughout the duration of the project are also included (see Section 3).

Fit within landscape and added value w.r.t. ongoing projects

Our project actively contributes to the activities clusters outlined by the TDCC-SSH in their Roadmap. More specifically, the contribution to activity clusters #1 and #5 can be summarised as follows:

Activity cluster #1. Increasing the percentage of findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (in short: FAIR) research data and software.

Our project aims at laying the foundation to ensure an easier implementation of the FAIR principles in the SSH, ensuring that both the technological systems and the human capacity building is adequately tailored to the needs of the field on the basis of a shared Action plan document.

Activity cluster #5. Building and maintaining an open and inclusive network organisation, involving all relevant parties, as a vehicle for making 1-4 happen.

The technical and organisational mapping (see WP1 & WP2), as well as the unconference (see WP3), will contribute to strengthening the network of relevant stakeholders for FAIR Implementation in the SSH.

The project has strong ties to activities carried out in existing institutes and infrastructure projects (e.g. DANS, ODISSEI, CLARIAH, RPOs), however it aims at tackling FAIR implementation more systematically and in a domain-wide fashion. Rather than creating something completely new, the aim is to make an inventory of such initiatives and make sure they are converging towards solving the bottlenecks. By doing so, the project and the Action plan towards FAIR implementation in the SSH that will stem from it offer guidance to these initiatives for steering future activities and investments. Nevertheless, excessive overlap is prevented by engaging relevant stakeholders in a timely manner and throughout the duration of the project. This is facilitated by the diverse composition of the project team in terms of roles and affiliations, and by maintaining an open channel of communication with the TDCC-SSH.

The project also seeks to create partnerships with other TDCC bottleneck projects. For instance, given the ambition of project #1 to promote the creation of FAIR data in the field of slavery and colonial archive studies, a partnership could be established - e.g. by including some of the datasets from their research community in the mapping of WP1 (tasks 2 and 3). Moreover, the project will collaborate closely with project #2, the results of which will inform in particular WP2.

Crucial to the success of the project is the active involvement and engagement of the SSH community, which will be constantly nurtured by the project team (see also section 2.3). In the preparatory phases, several representatives have been consulted, including the UKB RDM Working Group, CLARIAH's Interest Group on Curation, L-DCC coordinators, a Senior Data Management Expert, a Repository Product Owner as well as data stewards and other experts from DANS and SURF.

Those consulted have indicated they find this project "more than necessary" as they see FAIR implementation at technical, organisational, and domain levels as "chaotic" and highly "complex", marred by a "huge diversity in approaches" across institutions. At the same time, this project was found to be relevant not only for the SSH domain but also significant for FAIR implementation in RPOs across domains. As such, where there are gaps in FAIR implementation in other domains, we hope that our approach to harmonising FAIR services can serve as an example.

Part of the nuanced feedback the project team received were also points of attention for moving forward. One is the suggestion to address researchers as informal stakeholders in this project by taking into account researcher-led efforts to develop FAIR resources. Therefore, the organisational mapping (WP2) will strive to pinpoint research groups or researchers engaged in the development of FAIR resources and identify successes and gaps in FAIR services in RPOs. If we identify them, we will aim to include them in the FAIR technical mapping workshops (WP1).

Another suggestion was to tie the outcome of this project to the Recognition and Rewards program as a key nexus where both researchers and RPOs meet to determine involvement in Open Science practices, of which the development of FAIR resources takes prominence. The project team will consider different alternatives on how to connect our project to the R&R program, for example, by directly addressing R&R in the Call for Sessions of the Unconference.

2.2. Consortium, personnel and roles

Involved parties

The following parties will be involved in the project:

- **Erasmus University Rotterdam - Erasmus School of Social and Behavioral Sciences (EUR-ESSB)** is involved in the project as it hosts the **Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations (ODISSEI)**. ODISSEI provides data, skills and tools to conduct groundbreaking research in the field of (computational) social sciences by making sure that researchers and e-service providers work together. ODISSEI is also actively involved in facilitating FAIR Implementation in the social sciences and economics. Furthermore, the ODISSEI Coordination Team (ODISSEI CT) has a proven experience with managing projects involving multiple partners (e.g. ODISSEI Roadmap, SSHOC-NL). Members of the ODISSEI CT will lead WP4 (Coordination) and WP3 (Unconference and Action plan). Furthermore, EUR-ESSB hosts the **FAIR Expertise Hub for the Social Sciences**, a collaboration between ODISSEI and Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam funded by the Platform Digital Infrastructure (PDI-SSH) until the end of 2024. Thanks to the expertise acquired by working with FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) for over two years, combined with ad-hoc training received by the GOFAIR Foundation, members of the FAIR Hub will contribute in-kind to this project until the end of 2024, by assisting communities in filling in FIPs and generating insights into the technical implementation of the FAIR principles (see WP1).

- **DANS** (an institute that is part of the KNAW) will be involved in the project in two ways: both in its capacity of being the national centre of expertise and repository for research data, and as the partner responsible for the management of research data within the **CLARIAH-PLUS** consortium (to be succeeded by the **CLARIAH-NL** entity). DANS hosts a substantial number of RDM-experts. It is also a leading or collaborative partner in various national and European projects which aim to improve FAIRness in the research landscape, projects in which the RDM-experts are heavily involved. Notably, DANS has been the leading partner in the EU-funded FAIRsFAIR project, and is also in the lead in its successor project FAIR Impact. For this project, one of the RDM-experts employed by DANS will have a role in WP1, working closely with the Data manager.

- Thanks to the involvement of members of CLARIAH and ODISSEI, this project will also have close ties to **SSHOC-NL**, especially with the FAIR workstream. This will be fundamental to stay up-to-date with FAIR developments, especially from the INFRA's side. Within the FAIR-workstream of SSHOC-NL, preparations are currently made to set up a working group for the coordination of FAIR implementation within the SSHOC-NL ecosystem. Several of the participants in this project will also be involved in that SSHOC-NL working group, ensuring synergy and preventing redundancy.

- **Erasmus Research Services** has been established in 2020 at Erasmus University Rotterdam (EUR) to support excellence in research and research impact. It hosts the coordination of EUR's Local Digital Competence Center that is actively working towards maturity of its service portfolio, the certification of EUR's institutional repository, and the integration of FAIR-enablement in our long-term strategy. As a supporting structure to a primarily SSH-domain RPO, Erasmus Research Services has a high strategic interest in advancing the implementation of FAIR practices at community and domain level. To this end, ERS/L-DCC is a member of the **SURF Yoda consortium** that aims to facilitate the generation of FAIR data and the implementation of community-specific FAIR semantic resources. It also has completed internal and external FAIR-assessment projects, including the **FAIR-IMPACT FAIRness Assessment Challenge** and is a current participant in the **FAIR-enablement RPO Support Program by FAIR-IMPACT**.

Involved people

Name and title	Position	Role	Affil.
<i>Dr. T. Emery</i>	<i>Associate Professor</i>	<i>Project leader</i>	<i>EUR-ESSB</i>
<i>Dr. A.M. Maineri</i>	<i>Data manager</i>	<i>WP3: Coordination work towards Action plan WP3: Organization unconference WP1: Assisting with technical mapping WP2: Assisting with survey design for organisational mapping</i>	<i>EUR-ESSB</i>
<i>B. Lushaj, M.A.</i>	<i>Data steward</i>	<i>WP2: Leading the organisational mapping WP3: Organization unconference</i>	<i>EUR-ISS</i>
<i>Dr. J. Toubert</i>	<i>RDM Manager</i>	<i>WP1: Leading the technical mapping WP3: Organization unconference</i>	<i>DANS-KNAW</i>
<i>E. Krichever</i>	<i>Communication s manager</i>	<i>WP1: Communication and dissemination WP3: Logistics unconference WP3: Dissemination Action plan</i>	<i>EUR-ESSB</i>

<i>T. Canciu</i>	<i>Project manager</i>	<i>WP1: Project management WP3: Logistics unconference</i>	<i>EUR-ESSB</i>
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Requested positions

Name and title	Position	Role	Affil.
<i>to be determined</i>	Project manager	WP4: Project admin, monitoring and reporting	EUR-ESSB
Dr. A.M. Maineri	Data manager	WP3: Coordination work towards Action plan WP3: Organisation unconference WP1: Assisting with compiling FIPs for technical mapping WP2: Assisting with survey design for organizational mapping	EUR-ESSB
<i>to be determined</i>	RDM Expert	WP1: Comparing datasets against FIPs WP1: FAIR assessment	DANS-KNAW
B. Lushaj, M.A.	Research Data Steward	WP2: Developing Organizational Mapping Survey WP2: Conducting interviews with relevant stakeholders WP2: Analyzing and visualizing results	EUR-ERS
<i>to be determined</i>	Student assistant/intern	WP2: Setting up and analysing survey WP4: Help with logistics of unconference	EUR-ERS

Other team members

Dr. Tom Emery - **Project Leader**

Dr. Tom Emery, Director of ODISSEI and PI of SSHOC-NL, will serve as Project Lead for this project and contribute in-kind to ensure good coordination across partners as well as efficient communication with the stakeholders.

The project will also have an **Advisory Board**, which will be consulted for the most crucial phases of the project (e.g. reviewing outputs of the technical and organisational mappings before publication, reviewing the submissions to the call for sessions for the Unconference, reviewing the first draft of the Action plan). The following people agreed to participate so far:

- *Dr. Enno Meijers (National Library)*
- *Dr. Femmy Admiraal (Leiden University)*
- *Dr. Kees den Heijer (SURF)*
- *Dr. Coosje Veldkamp (Utrecht University)*

2.3. Communication strategy and dissemination

We see the communication and dissemination strategy as part and parcel of all work packages as crucial to our project's success is securing buy-in from the two stakeholder groups we have identified.

As such, the project members will be actively maintaining contacts with the relevant stakeholders throughout the duration of the project, e.g. via the mappings carried out in WP1 and WP2 and via the advisory board. We will strive as much as possible to join existing networks and meetings (e.g., L-DCC network) so as to avoid scheduling disruptions while at the same time receive feedback from multiple experts in an efficient manner.

Stakeholders include not only RDM practitioners (e.g. data stewards at universities), but also management at universities, representatives of funding agencies and other bodies who may be charged with implementing the recommendations stemming from the Action plan. We will engage with bodies such as the LBDI SSH (which advises the national council of SSH deans on infrastructure) to report our findings and keep our activities in tune with policy developments at a strategic level.

To ensure a wide reach, the results of the project will be made accessible via existing channels:

- 1) Dissemination of news and outputs via existing networks and groups the project members are part of, including for instance the Data Stewardship Interest Group (DSIG), the UKB workgroup Research Data, the SSHOC-NL Technical Working Group, Open Science Communities, and LCRDM. These will be the preferred channels to reach out to RDM practitioners, and to involve stakeholders in the mapping activities (WP1 and WP2) but also in the event and creation of the Action plan (WP3).
- 2) Dissemination of news and outputs via established social media accounts and newsletters of the project partners (e.g. ODISSEI newsletter, CLARIAH newsletter, etc.). These will be the preferred channels to engage the wider research community.
- 3) Participation in relevant national events on RDM, such the Dutch Open Science Festival, LCRDM, Recognition and Rewards festival, and project partners' conferences. This will be the preferred channel to maintain contacts with funders and e-infrastructure providers.

Project outputs will be openly published on accessible repositories (e.g. Zenodo).

Calendar of outreach and sharing of outputs

	Communication and Engagement Activities	Channels
Sep	WP1: Collaborative sessions with current SSH-participating institutes for FIPs WP1: Structured interviews for reconstructing institute specific Research Data Lifecycle WP1: Call for Participation to new SSH-participants for joining in WP1 WP2: Survey content and interview topics are shared with community for feedback; WP2: Communication with coordinators to check for existing meetings in the coming months	Targeted communication within SSHOC-NL DSIG Slack/Email DSIG Slack/Email
Oct	WP1: Collaborative sessions with current SSH-participating institutes for FIPs WP1: Structured interviews for reconstructing institute specific Research Data Lifecycle WP1: Call for Participation to new SSH-participants for joining in WP1 (cont.) WP2: Survey sent out WP2: Meetings for organisational mapping	Targeted communication within SSHOC-NL DSIG Slack/Email/Newsletters
Nov	WP1: Collaborative sessions with current SSH-participating institutes for FIPs WP1: Structured interviews for reconstructing institute specific Research Data Lifecycle WP1: FAIR assessment working sessions WP2: Meetings for organisational mapping	
Dec	WP1: Collaborative sessions with current SSH-participating institutes for FIPs WP1: Structured interviews for reconstructing institute specific Research Data Lifecycle WP1: FAIR assessment working sessions WP2: Meetings for organisational mapping	
Jan	WP1: FAIR assessment working sessions WP1: Present findings on FIP, Research Data Lifecycle and FAIR Assessment at events WP2: Meetings for organisational mapping	Open Science conferences, workshops, festivals
Feb	WP1: FAIR assessment working sessions WP1: Present findings on FIP, Research Data Lifecycle and FAIR Assessment at events WP3: Announcement "Save the date" for the Unconference	DSIG Slack/Newsletters and Social Media Open Science conferences, workshops, festivals

Mar	<p>WP1: Present findings on FIP, Research Data Lifecycle and FAIR Assessment at events</p> <p>WP1: Publish technical mapping as FAIR publication</p> <p>WP2: Results of organisational mapping shared</p> <p>WP2: Publish organizational mapping as FAIR publication</p> <p>WP3: Call for sessions for Unconference</p>	<p>Open Science conferences, workshops, festivals</p> <p>Open Access outlet (to be determined)</p> <p>DSIG Slack/UKB RDM WG meeting/OSC/Newsletters and Social Media/Zenodo</p> <p>Open Access outlet (to be determined)</p> <p>DSIG Slack/UKB RDM WG meeting/OSC/Newsletters and Social Media/Zenodo</p>
Apr	<p>WP3: Announcement program unconference</p>	<p>DSIG Slack/Newsletters and Social Media</p>
May	<p>WP3: Documentation Unconference</p> <p>WP3: Meetings for Action plan writing</p>	<p>Social media</p>
Jun	<p>WP3: Meetings for Action plan writing</p> <p>WP3: Invitation to publicly review Action plan</p>	<p>DSIG Slack/UKB RDM WG meeting/OSC/Newsletters and Social Media/Zenodo</p>
Jul	<p>WP3: Invitation to publicly review Action plan</p>	
Aug	<p>WP3: Dissemination of published Action plan</p>	<p>DSIG Slack/Newsletters and Social Media/Zenodo</p>

3. Financial information

[Omitted from this version]